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Effect of NaOH Concentration in Manufacture of Geopolymer Fly Ash Building Brick

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

Geopolymerization is a non-fired process of chemical reaction between silica, alumina, calcium, magnesium, iron bearing constituents of the material under alkaline condition to form hydrous structures of rock forming silicate minerals. In this research work geopolymerization technology was used for utilization of industrial solid wastes like fly ash in manufacture of high strength building brick. In this process, sodium based alkaline activator (pH > 11.5) consisting of anions of Cl⁻ and SO₄²⁻ of different concentrations in presence of water had been used for reaction of silica and silicates to develop a stable and solidified geopolymer structure by curing below 200°C and also at normal atmospheric temperature of 35°C. The raw mix consisting of 87% of fly ash and alkaline activator had been used by maintaining Na₂O/(Al₂O₃+SiO₂) ratio of 0.025 to 0.078 to manufacture building materials ranging in crushing strength of 6 to 48 MPa.

Keywords: Alumino-silicate polycondensation; exothermic reaction process; mineral dissolution; silicon-oxygen tetrahedral.

INTRODUCTION

Geopolymers are a member of the family of inorganic polymers, and are a chain structures formed on a backbone of Al and Si ions. It is a phenomenon that exists in the rock forming minerals of silicate family, having a series of geochemical reactions of mineral dissolution, aluminosilicate polycondensation and structural reorganization (Davidovits, 1991; Provis et al., 2005; Van Jaarsveld et al., 1991; Khalil and Merz, 1994). Geopolymers are a group of cement – like materials that are formed by reacting silica and alumina bearing materials with a solution of alkali and alkaline salts resulting into a mixture of gels and crystalline compounds that eventually harden into a new strong compound⁵. In the process of geopolymerization, silica and alumina bearing materials react in a solution of alkali and alkali salts resulting into a mixture of gels and crystalline compounds that eventually harden into a new and strong compound (Van Jaarsveld et al., 1995; Davidovits, 1994; Davidovits, 1994a; Lyon et al., 1996). Geopolymer concretes produced from calcined materials like fly ash generally yield high compressive strengths after curing at room temperature (Hardjito, 2004a). Geopolymers are also used for encapsulation and immobilization of hazardous or toxic wastes such as radioactive wastes, asbestos, and heavy metals (Comrie and Davidovits, 1988).

The geopolymerization process can be engineered on a wide variety of solid aluminosilicate raw materials for the synthesis of geopolymers. Among the potential solid aluminosilicate raw materials, industrial solid wastes such as fired-coal fly ash, alumina, red mud, metallurgical slag, building demolition materials, etc., are the most important raw materials (Swanepoel and Strydom, 2002; Wu and Sun, 2007; Panias, 2007; Van Jaarsveld et al., 2002; Cheng and Chiu 2010). This study is focused on the application of geopolymerization process by synthesis of rock forming mineral systems by alkali, alumina and silica reaction akin to natural rocks under atmospheric condition. Geopolymers are formed by the chemical fusion of alumina and silica bearing materials into concrete like products (Lyon et al., 1996; Davidovits 1988). It is an exothermic reaction process and carried out through oligomers in the form of unit structures for a three dimensional macromolecular network (Davidovits 1988). Like geopolymerization, many consider mineral polymerization as a similar concept in order to describe the process of making OH bearing polymer structures of silicon-oxygen tetrahedra with cations such as Ca, Al, Mg, Fe, Mn, Na, and K, etc. These form two-dimensional chains and three-dimensional network that typically occur in rock forming silicate minerals, hydrated portland cement, and slag systems. In either process, i.e., geopolymerization or mineral polymerization, [Si.O₄]⁴⁻ tetrahedra is the fundamental structural unit of these systems. Depending upon the nature of linkage and sharing of silicon-oxygen tetrahedra, the silicate minerals exist in isolated as well as continuous chain structures. The network formation of [Si.O₄]⁴⁻ tetrahedra by sharing of oxygen with the adjacent tetrahedra indicates the polymerization

structure. Polysialate, polysialate-siloxo and polysialate-disiloxo are the three important oligomeric structures for polymerization reaction.

Figure 1: Types of oligomeric structures

The amorphous to semi-crystalline three dimensional silico-aluminate structures as geopolymers based on silico-aluminate and further categorised the geopolymers structure based on the ratio of Si/Al shown in the as shown in Figure 1 was observed by Davidovits (2005). The chain structures of $[\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7]^{4-}$ tetrahedra with cations and neutralizing anions build the mineral polymer framework to achieve the strength. These silicate minerals with OH bearing characteristics possess excellent rock forming property akin to the calcium-silicate-hydrated structure that typically exists in hydrated Portland cement. Considering the industrial importance of these silicate minerals, a great deal of progress has been made on synthetic mineralization of silica and silicate bearing materials to make mineral polymers as structural and building materials.

The process of geopolymerization requires alkaline chemical activator for initiation of reaction in the formation of mineral polymer structures. Geopolymerization activators are strong alkalis of chemical salts of NaOH, KOH, Na_2SO_4 , Na_2CO_3 , K_2CO_3 , K_2SO_4 , small amount of cement clinker and water glass (Hardjito, 2004; Xiong et al., 2004; Khale, 2007). Dissolved sodium or potassium chloride salts have been used in the activator solution to retard the geopolymeric gel hardening and solidification Other chemical salts such as KCl, K_2CO_3 , $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and K_2HPO_4 are also used as activator for geopolymeric reaction and solidification (Brough et al 2000; Lee and Van Deventer 2002). The selection of different activators for alumino-silicate dissolution and its solidification into tetrahedral geopolymeric cementation structure is very important. In most cases, the alkaline reaction of alumino-silicates leads to formation of zeolite which is not a part of the cementation phase.

Thus combination of different anionic group activator with alkaline chemicals is quite important to build stable tetrahedral structure of alumino-silicate phases for development of strength. The potassium based chemicals are usually very costly and are not suitable for economic viability for the production of geopolymer materials. The sodium based alkaline chemicals are preferred and in such cases the formation of geopolymer matrix is temperature dependent. The curing of the product above normal atmospheric temperature is not a flexible option to adopt in commercial practice. Therefore, selection of proper chemicals with alkaline group for geopolymerization reaction at atmospheric temperature has been the focus of research. In such situation, the process is expected to be accepted as a green technology in manufacture of building material products.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Figure 2: The process steps.

The process for manufacture of fly ash based building materials follows the conventional method. To develop the process for manufacture of building brick and block, the powder raw material was used. In our approach, the raw material with a suitable mix design/composition was mixed in a pan mixer in presence of the alkaline activator and water. The process steps for manufacture of building fly ash brick is shown in Figure 2. The mixture was casted by compaction pressure of 20 ton to form standard size (230 × 110 × 75 mm) brick. The cast products are cured for setting at 20°C and under normal atmospheric condition (35°C) for comparison and standardization purpose. The principle of geopolymerization has been adopted by making different mix designs of fly ash where the reaction of fly ash with alkaline activator takes place mainly with silica and alumino-silicates. In this research work we have developed an alkaline activator after considering the importance of the role of activator in the geopolymerization process. The principle of geopolymerization has been adopted by making different mix designs of fly ash where the reaction of fly ash with alkaline activator takes place mainly with silica and alumino-silicates. In this research work we have developed an alkaline activator after considering the importance of the role of activator in the geopolymerization process.

Table - 1 Chemical analysis of fly ash

Constituent %	Na ₂ O	MgO	PO ₂ O ₅	SO ₃	CaO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	TiO ₂	Cr ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃
Fly ash	0.09	0.285	0.51	0.14	0.47	35.5	59.5	0.94	0.01	2.01

The manufacturing process of geopolymer fly ash building brick has been designed as: raw material preparation, activator addition and mixing, casting and demoulding followed by curing. Here we discuss the process of making a durable building material with any type of fly ash. The chemical analysis of fly ash has given in Table-1. The process is considered as a green process and it is successfully used for the manufacture of cold setting building products. The alkaline activator is sodium based that consist of anions of Cl⁻ and SO₄⁼ in different concentrations in water for reaction of silica and silicates to develop a stable mineral polymer structure (Nayak et al., 2009). The anion group chemicals act as the reactant in presence of sodium silicate as a set-modifier. The pH of the chemical activator consisting of sodium and anion group chemicals in water is above 11.5. The concentration of anion group chemicals in the activator is maintained depending on the chemical constitution of the oxides and silicates of aluminum, calcium, magnesium, iron bearing mineral phases which is needed for effective reaction.

Table- 2 Raw Material Mix Design

Raw material (wt. %)	Mix-1 (K1)	Mix-2 (K2)	Mix-3 (K3)	Mix – 4 (K4)	Mix – 5 (K5)
Fly ash	87	87	87	87	87
Activator solution	4	5	6	7	8
Water	9	8	7	6	5
$\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3+\text{SiO}_2)$	0.025	0.038	0.052	0.065	0.078

The concentration of SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 with respect to alkali (Na_2O) in the fly ash mix governs the geopolymerization reaction. The fly ash of 87% by weight was mixed with 4 to 8 % of alkaline activator solution of pH 11.5. Water was added up to 5 to 9% by weight to this mixture in order to form different mix compositions. The ratio of $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3+\text{SiO}_2)$ of different mixtures of alkaline activator and fly ash is given in Table-2. The different mix compositions such as Mix-1, Mix-2, etc., are also correspondingly designated as K series that are used in the text later.

RESULTS

Figure 3. Strength due to curing at 20°C. Figure 4. Strength due to curing at 35°C.

The fly ash used in experimental study contains very trace amount of oxides of Na, Mg, Ca, S, Mn, Cr, Ti and alumina and silica as major amount. Geopolymer reaction is dependent on temperature. The hardening of fly ash mix in the presence of alkaline activator generally takes a longer duration to attend the desired strength. Therefore, conditions of curing are the major aspects to develop a high quality geopolymer product. The bricks made out of different mix were cured by exposing to the air temperature at 20° and 35°C up to 25 days for the build-up of strength shown in Figure 3 and 4 respectively. It was observed that with the increase in alkaline activator and $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3+\text{SiO}_2)$ ratio the strength of fly ash product gradually increases. The fly ash mix consisting of $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3+\text{SiO}_2)$ ratio above 0.038 showed a remarkable increase in the strength. The strength gradually increased as the curing duration increases from 5 to 25 days. The product cured at 35°C under atmospheric conditions showed a higher value of compressive strength than the product cured at 20°C. It appeared that the dissolution reaction of fly ash in alkaline medium and formation of aluminosilicate polymer phases at 20°C was slow in comparison to the reaction process at 35°C. It was observed that the bricks at different alkali ratio attain the maximum crushing strength in 30 to 25 days of curing at 20° and 35°C respectively. This observation on the development of strength indicates that alkaline activator consisting of anions of Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} was effective at atmospheric temperature and below ranging between 20 to 35°C. The substantial increase of strength of fly ash mix was due to the increase of alkali concentration and formation of alkaline aluminosilicate phases. The X-ray diffraction study shown in Figure 5 shows the intensity corresponding to alkaline aluminosilicate phases in different fly ash mix. The sample K0 represents the fly ash used in preparation of different mix with alkaline activator (base material).

Figure 5: Showing X- ray diffraction pattern of fly ash and geopolymer fly ash products.

Alumina and silica are the major chemical constituents of fly ash which exist in the form of quartz (SiO_2) and mullite ($3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$) mineral phases. From the XRD data it is assumed that analcime, sodalite, cancrinite, natrolite, herschelite, and mullite, as predominant mineral phases in K1 to K5 mix design. The electron micrograph of a fully reacted solidified fly ash product obtained from K5 mixture was shown in Figure 6(a). The elemental distribution of the crystalline acicular structures of sodium aluminum silicate phases observed under EDX (Figure 6.b) and the elemental analysis of the crystalline phases of the Na-crosslinked geopolymer had shown in Table-3 .

DISCUSSION

The fly ash used is a burnt mineral residue of pulverized coal used in thermal power plant. It is a compound of silica, alumina, and also contain minor amounts of other oxides such as Fe, Na, Ca, Mg, and K, etc. In the geopolymerization process, the silica and alumina bearing minerals of fly ash react with the soluble alkalis at ambient temperature to form the geopolymer minerals in presence of anions of Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} . By atmospheric curing, minerals of silica in the form of quartz and alumino-silicate in the form of mullite react with alkali activator. The reaction proceeds through gradual dissolution of silica and alumina depending upon the concentration of alkali. With increase of alkali concentration (from K1 to K5), the formation of alkali alumino-silicates have increased due to dissolution of quartz and mullite phases present in the fly ash. The formation of alkali alumino-silicates is distinct in the fly ash mix K3, K4 and K5 as seen from the XRD data. The other mineral phases are mostly hydrous alkali alumino-silicates which resembles to analcime sodalite, cancrinite natrolite and herschelite minerals. The formation of these phases is expected due to different substitution of H_2O , Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} ions. Chemical reactions between oxide phases of silica and alumina under alkaline condition form OH bearing sodium-aluminium-silicate structures which on solidification develops the binding strength (Lee W.K.W. and Van Deventer J.S.J., 2002a,).

In geopolymerization process SO_4^{2-} is an effective ion of higher hydration energy which promotes hydration of silicates, aluminates and alkalis and enhances the interactions of monomers in formation of crystalline phases (Wang et al., 2006 ; Desbats-Le Chequer and Frizon, 2011). The Cl^- ion acts as an accilator in gel formation and helps in crystallization (Lee and Van Deventer, 2002a; Desbats-Le Chequer and Frizon, 2011). The polymerization process involves a substantially fast chemical reaction under alkaline condition with Si and Al bearing minerals that results in the three dimensional polymeric chain and ring structures of Si-O-Al-O monomers. Al and Si co-ordinates with oxygen atoms, and therefore, the presence of cations such as Na^+ is essential to maintain the electric neutrality in the geopolymeric matrix. The mechanism of setting and hardening of the geopolymer material comprises of two steps: first, activation by an alkaline solution to form reactive monomers or oligomers, and second, polycondensation to build the alumino-silicate network structures.

The geopolymeric reaction of alumina, silica and silicates in presence of alkali takes place (Changgao) 1992 as follows

Based on the above principles fly ash has been used to manufacture cold setting building bricks and blocks. Fly ash has been used up to 87% by weight of the total mix by maintaining $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{SiO}_2)$ ratio between 0.025 and 0.078 in presence of an alkaline activator. In this type of fly ash mix, the solidified product under atmospheric curing attains a crushing strength as high as 48 MPa. The process has been implemented for economic production of high volume (87%) fly ash building bricks by maintaining $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{SiO}_2)$ ratio 0.025 to 0.038. The fly ash building bricks of size 230×110×75 mm produced by hydraulic compaction after 25 days of atmospheric curing weigh in the range of 2.80 to 3.20 kg after 8 to 11% of water absorption and attain up to 10 MPa crushing strength. The fly ash mix with $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{SiO}_2)$ ratio between 0.052 to 0.078 are used for manufacture of high strength bricks, blocks, and concrete

Table- 3 Elemental analysis of the crystalline phases corresponding to the EDX image of Na-crosslinked geopolymer showing fully reacted regions of mix K5 (average analysis)

Element	Weight %	Atomic %	Compound %	Formula
Na	24.29	24.25	32.74	Na_2O
Al	12.25	10.42	23.14	Al_2O_3
Si	7.61	6.22	16.29	SiO_2
Ti	3.07	1.47	5.12	TiO_2
Fe	17.66	7.26	22.72	FeO
O	35.13	50.39		

Figure 6 (a). SEM image of Na-crosslinked geopolymer showing fully reacted regions of mix K5 (Fly ash –87% and $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{SiO}_2)$ mix ratio-0.078).

Figure 6 (b). EDX analysis showing elemental distribution of cross linked crystalline phases (Fly ash –87% and $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{SiO}_2)$ ratio – 0.078).

The electron micrograph of a fully reacted solidified fly ash product obtained from K5 mixture as given in Figure 6(a) shows the formation of crystalline structures of sodium assisted cross linked aluminosilicate geopolymer phases. These alkaline phases occur in acicular form and seem to have cross linked into a matrix in the solidified product. The elemental distribution of the crystalline acicular structures of sodium aluminum silicate phases observed under EDX is given in Figure 6(b) shows that the crystalline phases of acicular structure of Na-crosslinked geopolymer bears the elements like Na, Al, and Si (given in Table 3), which correspond to the geopolymer phase of sodium aluminum silicate. The micrography study it is observed that the reaction of fly ash in alkaline activator consisting of anions of Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} form crystalline grains of sodium aluminum silicates. These grains of sodium aluminum silicates with minor to trace amounts of Fe, Ti, S, Mg, Ca, and K are mostly fibrous and elongated. These mineral phases with different cation and anion substitution grow into amorphous to crystalline structures by dissolution and solidification. Inter-coordination of the polymerized minerals helps in the build-up of the cementation property. Depending upon the bonding strength the geopolymerisation process is flexible to make high strength building bricks ranging crushing strength from 7 to 12 MPa. Use of suitable geopolymer activator in manufacture of building brick is an eco-friendly non fired carbon negative process.

CONCLUSION

We have shown that by using the Geopolymerization process, several types of building materials such as bricks and blocks can be made for commercial exploitation using fly ash. The fly ash based building bricks confirm to Indian standard. We have found that the reaction process of geopolymerization depends on the type of raw materials and on the concentration of alkaline activator. The sodium based alkaline activator ($\text{pH} > 11.5$) consisting of anions of Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} is the most effective one to inhibit the reaction process and help in attaining the desired strength. The compressive strength increases with the increase of $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{SiO}_2)$ ratio, which is dependent on concentration of NaOH. The microstructure of geopolymer products resembles a typical crystalline material with the increasing NaOH concentration. The crystallinity is due to the dissolution of silica and alumina followed by polycondensation. The dissolution of aluminosilicates in the raw material has been noticed from the changes in XRD patterns as a function of curing time and NaOH concentration. Finally, we have found that the geopolymerization process is a green technology as it aims for 100% utilization of waste materials.

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